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Development of Project-based Learning (PBL) for Internet of Things

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ABSTRACT

An increasing number of physical objects are being connected to the Internet realizing the idea of the so-called Internet of Things (IoT). A basic example is the idea of smart homes. There are also other domains in which the IoT can play an important role and improve the quality of our lives. These applications include transportation, healthcare, industrial automation, and emergency response. Since project-based learning (PBL) provides contextualized and authentic learning, which has been demonstrated to foster higher order thinking while promoting acquisition of content-area knowledge, this project applies PBL for learning of IoT application development. A PBL curriculum was designed to emphasize a real-world problem (specifically, designing a smart watch for monitoring the state of pressure and the quality of the sleep) while enhancing learning motivation, learning emotion and performance, and fostering the creativity and problem-solving skills necessary for innovation and excellence in the learners' future professional careers as IoT application developers. The study will adopt a pretest and posttest quasi-experimental design. Over an 16-week intervention, the control group will receive traditional instructions while the experimental group will receive PBL instructions. Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) will be used to compare the learning outcomes of the two research groups. This study will explore how different teaching strategies affect students' creativity and problem-solving skills and, at the same time, acquiring engineering knowledge for developing IoT applications.

- Conference Key Areas: Sustainability and Engineering Education, Curriculum Development, Engineering Education Research

Keywords: Internet of things (IoT), project-based learning, creativity, problem-solving

INTRODUCTION

As an emerging technology, the Internet of Things (IoT) is expected to offer promising solutions TO transform the operation and role of many existing industrial systems such as transportation systems and manufacturing systems. For example, when IoT is used for creating intelligent transportation systems, the transportation authority will be able to track each vehicle's existing location, monitor its movement, and predict its future location and possible road traffic. The term IoT was initially proposed to refer to uniquely identifiable interoperable connected objects with radio-frequency identification (RFID) technology [1]. Later on, researchers relate IoT with more technologies such as sensors, actuators, GPS devices, and mobile devices. Today, a commonly accepted definition for IoT is a dynamic global network infrastructure with self-configuring capabilities based on standard and interoperable communication protocols where physical and virtual 'Things', with intelligent interfaces, have identities, physical attributes, virtual personalities, and are seamlessly integrated into the information network [2].

The IoT enables physical objects to see, hear, think and perform jobs by having them "talk" together, to share information and to coordinate decisions. The IoT transforms these objects from being traditional to smart by exploiting its underlying technologies such as ubiquitous and pervasive computing, embedded devices, communication technologies, sensor networks, Internet protocols and applications. Smart objects along with their supposed tasks constitute domain specific applications (vertical markets) while ubiquitous computing and analytical services form application domain independent services (horizontal markets). Conceptually speaking, every domain specific application is interacting with domain independent services, whereas in each domain sensors and actuators communicate directly with each other. Over time, the IoT is expected to have significant home and business applications, to contribute to the quality of life and to grow the world's economy. For example, smart-homes will enable their residents to automatically open their garage when reaching home, prepare their coffee, control climate control systems, TVs and other appliances. In order to realize this potential growth, emerging technologies and innovations, and service applications need to grow proportionally to match market demands and customer needs. Furthermore, devices need to be developed to fit customer requirements in terms of availability anywhere and anytime. Also, new protocols are required for communication compatibility between heterogeneous things (living things, vehicles, phones, appliances, goods, etc.).

Since project-based learning (PBL) provides contextualized and authentic learning, which has been demonstrated to foster higher order thinking while promoting acquisition of content-area knowledge, this study applies PBL to learning of Internet of Things (IoT). A PBL curriculum was designed to expose students to real-world problems, deepen their academic knowledge while exploring, and further enhance students' learning motivation, learning emotion and performance, and creativity skills [3]. For college education, courses that require great amounts of hands-on experience

extensively adopt PBL to cement students' practical use of knowledge. However, to better prepare students for the future challenges, traditional PBL can be enhanced by specifically integrating creativity skills. To serve this purpose, this study adopted Creativity-enhanced PBL, emphasizing the training and development of creative thinking, and using a real world issue – Design and implementation of IoT devices for different domain-specific applications – to foster problem solving (PS) skills [4]. The goal of fostering creativity in instructions is to promote divergent thinking [5] and to guide students to develop the ability and intention to develop innovative solutions to problems.

THE DESIGN OF RESEARCH EXPERIEMNTS

This study adopted a pretest and posttest quasi-experimental design. The experiment design is illustrated in *Figure 1*. The independent variable was the instructional strategy, either Creativity-Enhanced PBL (the experimental group) or traditional PBL instruction (the control group). The dependent variables were students' engineering knowledge for IoT design, problem solving skill, creative thinking capability, and learning motivation.

Figure 1. Experiment Design

1 SUBJECT RECRUITMENT

Subjects for this study were recruited from an undergraduate course offered at a large university in Taiwan. Forty-eight students registering for the course “Design and implementation of IoT applications” were randomly assigned to one of these two groups.

2. EXPERIMENT PROCEDURES

The duration of the experiment was twenty-four weeks, over the course of two semesters (i.e. twelve weeks for each semester) . The students enrolled in the first semester were assigned to the control group (C) while the students enrolled in the second semester were assigned to the experimental group (E). The number of students in the control group and experimental group are 23 and 25 respectively. The age of students range from 21 to 23 years old. The percentages of female students in

the control group and experimental group are 24% and 25% respectively. Four tests were given as pretests, including a test about the knowledge related to IoT (e.g. understanding of sensors, network protocols and embedded systems, etc), the Abbreviated Torrance Test for Adults (ATTA), Creative Problem Solving Test (CPST), and Motivated Strategies for Learning Questionnaire (MSLQ).

The course was designed to emphasize the real-world IoT problems in design and implementation using the production of an IoT system for healthcare as a case study through in-class lectures, user studies, and laboratory experiments. In-class lectures included topics such as working principles of the sensors, network protocols, data management and the use of various open-source software and hardware such as Arduino, Android, Hadoop, etc., covering professional knowledge required for making a real-world IoT application and system. User studies were designed for the students to understand practical issues by interacting with real ordinary users, while laboratory experiments were aimed at evaluating the mechanisms of any of the design strategies, e.g. issues related to user-friendliness and energy saving .

In the first weeks of the course, each group attended the class to take the pretests and receive an introduction to the curriculum. Beginning at the second week, the course proceeded with lectures covering basic knowledge of designing and implementing IoT systems, such as sensor selection, UI design, and network protocols. For the fifth and sixth week, the problem context was introduced to both groups: How to design and implement an IoT system for sleep-stage monitoring with an accuracy greater than 85 percent.

At this point the instructional strategies for the two groups diverged. For the control group (C), the lecturer adopted traditional PBL by leading group discussion sessions about power saving, physiological signals processing, user interface design, database management, etc.; for the experimental group (E), creativity-enhanced PBL was augmented with a group brainstorming activity—card exchange. In a group of three, one student, based on the problem the lecturer gave, noted down his/her idea on a card with a blue pen, then passed the card to the other group members and continued to add more thoughts on the card. If the member has any idea similar to the previous ones, he/she could use a red pen to add more concrete and specific thought on the card. In the end of the class, the lecturer shared all the ideas with the class by projecting the cards from every group on the screen. After class, students discussed ideas on the card they wrote in class in the time for independent study, using a mind map [6] to reorganize their brainstorming.

For creativity-enhanced PBL, the lecturer provided a real world problem related to the use of smartwatch for pressure and sleep monitoring, assisted with proper creative thinking skills and a web quest. All the group members worked together to decide how to develop and implement such an application based on IoT technologies, think up possible solutions and revise the solution based on feedback. In class, in addition to direct instructions of IoT-related course contents, the lecturer provided students with creative thinking skills and group discussion guidance as scaffolding; outside of class students met in groups every week to gather the information needed for class discussion time. The activities for the PBL group (C) and Creativity-enhanced PBL group (E) were shown in *Table 1*.

Table 1. Summary of instructional activities and time allocation for the control group (C) and experimental group (E)

Instructional Activities	Control Group (C): Project-based Learning (PBL)	Experimental Group (E): Creativity-enhanced PBL
Content delivery	PPT-assisted instruction (30%)	PPT-assisted instruction (10%)
Group Discussion	Lecturer-led Group Discussion and Class Presentation (15%)	In- and outside-classroom group discussion and Class Presentation (15%)
		Feedback from the lecturer (5%)
Creative thinking and Problem solving tasks		Group brainstorming based on card- exchange (15%)
Outside the classroom activities	User study (5%)	User study (5%)
	Independent study (40%)	Independent study (40%)
Assessment	Project Presentation (10%)	Project Presentation (10%)

3. DATA ANALYSES

Both quantitative and qualitative data will be collected for this study. Descriptive statistics will be used to describe the means, standard deviations, and adjusted means for the tests between the two groups. Next, analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) will be used to compare the final results between the control group and the experimental group at the end of this study, with pretest scores as covariates to eliminate the effect of any existing pretest differences in the results. For the qualitative evaluation, data will be collected from feedback forms during the last week of the class, through which we know students' acceptance of teaching strategies and how much improvement the students thought they can make.

4. DISCUSSION

At the end of this study, five respective descriptive statistics from the experimental group and the control group will be received. With the statistics, contrasts between pretest and posttest as well as the between-group comparison can be made. We hope that some expected results can be observed through these data.

1) Given that both groups used the same teaching material, the contrast between pretest and posttest from both groups can tell the content validity of teaching materials.

2) Receiving PBL instruction on the same project, both groups are expected to make improvement in obtaining basic knowledge of designing and implementing IoT systems.

3) Because the two groups adopted different teaching strategies, the contrast can be made by comparing the posttest results to see whether creativity-enhanced PBL can help students deepen their knowledge on the design and implementation of IoT systems and, at the same time, achieve a higher level goal – improved solving skills and creative thinking capabilities.

4) By involving creative thinking skills in PBL instruction, students' skill in designing and implementing IoT systems, along with their learning motivation can be

effectively improved. With such results, this research might be expanded and further analysis can be done. Hopefully, this creativity-enhanced PBL teaching strategy can make contribution and be extensively applied in all courses in Department of Computer Science. We expect students to be active and efficient learners whose potentials can be fully discovered through this intriguing and inspiring teaching strategy.

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